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Synthesis of new MIL-101(Cr)/ZnCdO₂ nanocomposite catalyst for the sonodecomposition of rhodamine B (RhB) organic dye

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Abstract

MIL-101(Cr) metal organic framework is considered as a unique material and has been extremely investigated for the potential applications in multiple areas. In this work, MIL-101(Cr)/ZnCdO₂ nanocomposite was fabricated via the hydrothermal method and identified using FESEM, EDAX, XRD and FTIR. The sonocatalytic features of the as-gained MIL-101(Cr)/ZnCdO₂ nanocomposite was evaluated by degrading rhodamine B (RhB) dye under H₂O₂-ultrasonic (US) system from water solution. Several analytical factors, such as contact time, catalyst dosage, initial RhB concentration and initial H₂O₂ concentration were assessed to obtain the maximum sonocatalytic efficiency. Regarding the obtained data, the decomposition efficiency reached to be 97.3%. Moreover, the trapping experiments illustrated that ·OH radicals were the main reactive species in the RhB decomposition. Hence, MIL-101(Cr)/ZnCdO₂ nanocomposite reveals excellent sonocatalytic activity under US irradiation, implying promising application in sewage remediation.

Keywords: MIL-101(Cr)/ZnCdO₂, metal organic framework, nanocomposite, sonocatalyst, RhB dye, sonodecomposition.